

POSITION PAPER ON FARM INPUT SUBSIDY PROGRAM (FISP/AFFORDABLE INPUT SUBSIDY PROGRAM AIP) IN MALAWI

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ABSTRACT

The Farm Input Subsidy Program (FISP) was introduced in Malawi in 2005 as a response to recurring food shortages and aims to improve food security by providing smallholder farmers with access to essential agricultural inputs such as fertilizers and seeds (ChibwanaC, 2023). By supporting vulnerable farmers the program targets resource-poor smallholder farmers, with a focus on vulnerable groups, ensuring they receive the necessary inputs to improve their agricultural output (ROBERT, 2017). This paper examines FISP and AIP, its background and history, how it was implemented in Malawi, how it address poverty and livelihood issues and it also highlighting their benefits and challenges as well as recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the backbone of Malawi's economy, sustaining the livelihoods of approximately 80% of the population and contributing substantially to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and foreign exchange earnings (Chirwa, 2011). The sector is dominated by smallholder farmers who primarily cultivate maize, the country's staple crop, as a source of both food and income. Despite its centrality, Malawi's agriculture sector faces persistent challenges, including declining soil fertility, limited access to quality seeds and fertilizers, inadequate financial resources, and vulnerability to climatic shocks, such as droughts and floods (Dorward et al., 2008).

In response, the Malawian government introduced and implemented agricultural input subsidy programs aimed at increasing productivity, stabilizing household food security, and improving rural livelihoods (CHIWRA, 2011). Among these was the Farm Input Subsidy Program (FISP) that was launched in 2005 and the Affordable Input Subsidy Program (AIP) which was initiated in 2020. Both initiatives aim to enhance access to agricultural inputs such as fertilizer and improved seed, thereby boosting crop productivity, improving household food security, and reducing rural poverty. The programs enhance household food security, boost rural livelihoods, and contribute to national economic stability. However, their effectiveness and sustainability depend on improved targeting, integration with extension services, robust monitoring, and fiscal planning.

Historical Background of Agricultural Input Subsidy Programs in Malawi

The concept of subsidizing agricultural inputs in Malawi began in the late 1990s following the 1996–1997 food crisis, which exposed the vulnerability of smallholder farmers to climatic and market shocks. The Starter Pack Program (SPP), launched in 1998, provided farmers with maize seeds and fertilizers sufficient for half an acre of maize cultivation, aiming to promote self-reliance and improve national food security (CHIWRA, 2011). The program was widely praised for mitigating food shortages, although concerns emerged regarding equitable targeting and inclusion of the ultra-poor.

The Starter Pack evolved into the Targeted Inputs Program (TIP), which attempted to prioritize vulnerable households more effectively. However, TIP still faced challenges in accurately identifying beneficiaries, leaving some of the poorest farmers without access to essential inputs. These limitations set the stage for the launch of FISP in 2005.

FISP represented a significant policy shift, aiming to provide a larger-scale distribution of subsidized fertilizers and maize seeds to millions of smallholder farmers. By 2014–2015, the program reached over 2 million households, with significant improvements in maize yields reported in districts such as Mchinji, Ntcheu, Dedza, and Kasungu (MASON N., 2013). Despite these successes, FISP faced criticism regarding political interference in beneficiary selection, delayed input delivery, and limited inclusion of the most vulnerable households (CHIWRA, 2011).

In 2020, the Affordable Input Subsidy Program (AIP) was introduced as FISP's successor. AIP retained the core objectives of increasing access to inputs but introduced more stringent targeting mechanisms aimed at ultra-poor and marginalized farmers. While AIP retained the core principle of input subsidies, it broadened access and adjusted its design features to accommodate a larger number of households (De Weerd and Duchoslav 2022). Additionally, AIP expanded support to include crops such as sorghum and rice, promoting diversification and reducing reliance on maize. The program emphasized equitable distribution, cost-effectiveness, and long-term sustainability while maintaining the goal of improving household food security and agricultural productivity (World Bank, 2019).

IMPLEMENTATION OF FISP OR AIP IN MALAWI

The implementation of Malawi's Farm Input Subsidy Program (FISP) and the Affordable Input Program (AIP), followed a series of coordinated steps. These steps were designed to achieve food security by making agricultural inputs accessible to smallholder farmers. The implementation of the FISP evolved through phases of targeting, distribution, and reformed to AIP. The primary purpose of the program was to increase resources for smallholder farmer's access to improved agricultural farm inputs in order to achieve food self-sufficiency and increase income through enhanced maize production (ASFAW, 2017).

The Farm Input Subsidy Program (FISP) was implemented in Malawi starting in the early 2005 to 2006 agricultural season in response to severe food shortages. The program used a voucher system to provide subsidized agricultural inputs, primarily fertilizer and improved seeds, to millions of resource-poor smallholder farmers (DORWARD, 2011). The program's design began with the Ministry of Agriculture and other government departments. The government allocated a significant portion of its national budget to the program, often also securing donor support (WALLS, 2023). The size of the subsidy, the number of targeted beneficiaries, and the types of inputs to be subsidized primarily fertilizer and maize seed were determined in this phase.

The Initial implementation was from 2005 to 2015. The program originally aimed to target approximately 50% of the rural population, focusing on productive poor households. The targeting process was initially re-organized and a community-based targeting approach was used (LUNDUKA, 2014). The process of identifying the households is facilitated by the agricultural

development staff. It then moved to the Traditional authority, Village headmen, with the help of local committees such as Village Development Committees and village Agriculture committees. They would then create the lists of vulnerable households to receive paper coupons. The list of the vulnerable households was then given to the agriculture development staff to report back to the government. Then the coupons were then distributed to the farmers (ASFAW, 2017). The process was designed to ensure that the poorest farmers who could not afford inputs at market price were prioritized.

FISP provided coupons for subsidized inorganic fertilizer e.g. NPK and urea as well as improved seeds, initially focusing on maize and later expanding to include legume seeds from 2008. Farmers with coupons could redeem them for a heavily discounted price for a fixed quantity of inputs (DORWARD, 2011). The private agro-dealers would then submit the redeemed coupons to the government for reimbursement.

In its first decade, the distribution of inputs was primarily handled by two government agencies namely the Agricultural Development and Marketing Corporation (ADMARC) and the Smallholder Farmers Fertilizer Revolving Fund of Malawi (SFFRFM). While the inputs were heavily subsidized, farmers were required to pay a small contribution to redeem their vouchers (ASFAW, 2017).

Facing issues of inefficiency and exclusive seizures, the government implemented major reforms in the 2016/17 season. The community-based targeting approach by local leaders was replaced with a centrally managed, more randomized beneficiary selection system to reduce bias (ASFAW, 2017). The total number of beneficiaries was also reduced. The government increased the role of a mix of public and private entities in fertilizer distribution and retailing through a competitive bidding process.

The government, through the Ministry of Agriculture and other departments, managed the program's overall policy. Contracts were awarded to numerous private companies, as well as state-owned enterprises like ADMARC and SFFRFM, for the supply, warehousing, and retail of inputs. This was a critical step to ensure that the required quantities of fertilizer and seed were available in the country before the planting season (CHIRWA, 2013). This was intended to improve efficiency, availability, and reduce travel distances for farmers. Farmers were required to pay a

larger, variable co-payment for their inputs, which was designed to increase financial sustainability and create competition among suppliers.

In 2020, the new Malawian government replaced the FISP with the Affordable Inputs Program (AIP). Recognizing the extensive corruption and logistical challenges of the paper-based coupon system, the government introduced the Affordable Input Program (AIP). A key reform was the shift to a digital system (NYONDO, 2021). The AIP took a more universal approach, extending subsidies to all smallholder farmers, and expanded the range of subsidized seeds to include sorghum and rice.

The AIP continued to use a coupon or voucher system similar to the FISP. Beneficiaries were identified using their national ID cards, the farmers' national IDs are linked to the system and redemption was handled electronically at agro-dealer shops, ADMARC and small holder set light depots using their ID. The goal was to eliminate the black market for coupons and improve transparency (NYONDO, 2021). Although AIP and FISP had different scopes and budgetary implications, they shared the overarching goals of increasing agricultural productivity, improving food security, and providing social protection for poor farming households. AIP is therefore best understood as a continuation and reform of FISP rather than a wholly separate initiative.

THE ADVATAGES OF FISP AND AIP

Increased fertilizer use and maize productivity, both FISP and AIP significantly increased the adoption of fertilizer and improved seed varieties among smallholder farmers. Studies demonstrate that the provision of subsidized inputs resulted in higher maize yields, particularly during the early years of FISP when program design and delivery were relatively effective (Liverpool-Tasie and Ricker-Gilbert 2015). At the national level, these productivity gains contributed to higher maize production, which remains central to Malawi's food system

FISP and AIP assisted in the Short-term market stabilization, by increasing maize production in years with favorable rainfall, FISP and AIP contributed to stabilizing domestic market maize supply. This helped moderate the prices of maize on the market, with 1kg of maize selling at 320 to 350mkw and a bag of maize was retailing at mkw32, 000. Thereby benefitting both subsidy recipients and non-recipients who purchased maize on the open market (Pauw and Thurlow,

2014). Market stability was particularly important in protecting poor households from the adverse effects of food inflation.

Wider access and social protection specifically with AIP. Unlike FISP, which targeted fewer households, AIP extended access to subsidized inputs to a broader segment of the rural population. This expansion explicitly combined productivity objectives with social protection, especially during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the global surge in fertilizer prices (Malawi National Planning Commission 2024). By acting as a safety net, AIP cushioned poorer households who would otherwise have been excluded from input use, reducing vulnerability to shocks.

Policy and institutional learning, both FISP and AIP provided platforms for testing innovations such as electronic voucher systems and beneficiary registration databases. These experiences have contributed to institutional learning and capacity building in Malawi's broader social assistance landscape (De Weerd and Duchoslav 2022). Such innovations can inform the design of future agricultural and welfare programs.

DISADVANTAGES OF FISP AND AIP

High fiscal burden is the first disadvantage of FISP and AIP. One of the most significant criticisms of both FISP and AIP lies in their high fiscal cost. Subsidies consumed a substantial portion of Malawi's agricultural budget, often exceeding 60%, thereby limiting investment in other essential areas such as irrigation, extension services, and rural infrastructure (ActionAid Malawi 2023). During years of high global fertilizer prices, such as 2021/22, fiscal pressures became particularly acute, leading to debt accumulation and budgetary imbalances.

Targeting challenges and leakages, despite efforts to establish beneficiary registers, both programs struggled with targeting inefficiencies. Issues such as elite capture, inclusion of non-poor households, ghost beneficiaries, and delayed distribution were widespread (Dorward and Chirwa 2014). These errors not only undermined program equity but also reduced overall impact.

Market distortions by the government. By dominating input distribution, the government crowded out private agro-dealers, weakening incentives for private-sector development in fertilizer and seed markets. This lack of competition reduced efficiency and innovation within the agricultural input sector (Jayne et al. 2018). Such distortions may have long-term implications for private-sector participation in Malawi's agricultural transformation.

In addition to this is Governance and implementation weaknesses. Governance lapses significantly constrained AIP in particular. Procurement controversies, such as the widely publicized 2022 “botched” fertilizer deal, exposed weaknesses in accountability and transparency (Malawi Office of the Ombudsman 2024; The Nation Online 2025). Implementation inefficiencies often delayed input delivery, reducing the timeliness and effectiveness of the subsidies. Such governance failures eroded public trust and highlighted the vulnerability of subsidy program to political interference.

Lastly on the disadvantages of FISP and AIP is agronomic risks. The heavy focus on maize and chemical fertilizer use encouraged mono-cropping, which undermined crop diversification and resilience. Without complementary investments in soil fertility management and extension services, fertilizer response rates declined over time, limiting the sustainability of productivity gains (IFPRI 2022). This raises concerns about soil degradation and the long-term ecological viability of Malawi’s agricultural system.

HOW FISP AND AIP ADDRESS POVERTY AND LIVELIHOOD ISSUES IN MALAWI

A primary impact of these programs is the substantial increase in agricultural productivity. By making fertilizer and hybrid maize seeds affordable, this intervention enables smallholders to increase maize yields, Malawi’s staple crop, which directly enhances household food availability (Chinsinga & Poulton, 2014). The result is a greater overall crop production, which, in the early years of FISP, contributed to significant national maize surpluses, which helped stabilize maize prices and reduced hunger at household and community levels (Dorward & Chirwa, 2011). By reducing the risk of chronic food shortages, the program provides a buffer against one of the core drivers of poverty in Malawi. These programs also indirectly encourage farmers to adopt more modern farming techniques, further boosting their productivity and moving them away from subsistence-only farming methods.

This boost in food production directly translates to enhanced food security and improved nutrition for participating households. When a family can produce more food on their own farm, they are less likely to experience food shortages, especially during the lean season (LUNDUKA, 2014). Furthermore, the inclusion of legumes and other crops in the subsidy program, particularly during the FISP era, has been shown to improve household dietary diversity and nutritional outcomes, especially among children. This diversification of crops helps to ensure that families have access

to a wider range of nutritious foods, not just maize.

The economic benefits of FISP and AIP are also significant. The increase in agricultural output allows farmers to not only feed their families but also to sell any surplus produce. This generates a direct cash income, which, combined with the savings from not having to buy expensive food, significantly increases a household's real income and consumption. The additional income can be used to pay for school fees, healthcare, and other essential services, thereby contributing to human development outcomes (Denning et al., 2009). Early studies of the FISP program confirmed that it led to increase per-capita consumption among the poorest farmers. Additionally, the programs create broader economic benefits by stimulating the agricultural sector and related industries, such as input distribution and agro-dealerships, which in turn creates employment opportunities.

Both FISP and AIP have been crucial in building household resilience against shocks like droughts or floods. With larger harvests, farming families are able to build up food reserves that act as a buffer against periods of food scarcity. This enhanced resilience helps to prevent households from falling deeper into poverty during climate-related crises. A notable social benefit is the reduced need for vulnerable individuals, particularly women, to engage in precarious, low-paying casual labor (locally known as *ganyu*) to earn money for food during the hungry season, thereby protecting them from exploitation and freeing up their time for other productive activities (CHIWRA, 2011).

Finally, FISP and AIP also play a role in social protection and the programs have been shown to empower marginalized groups, especially women. Although targeting has its flaws, research on FISP found that female-headed households who received input coupons experienced tangible improvements in their household's nutritional status (ROBERT, 2017). Unlike cash transfers, which can be consumed quickly, input subsidies have the potential to generate longer-term benefits by increasing productivity and ensuring food self-reliance. The subsidy program provides a critical pathway for resource-poor households to access productive resources they could not otherwise afford, giving them a dynamic tool to improve their immediate livelihoods and enhance their food security.

At the community level, increased maize production has spillover benefits for rural economies. Input subsidies stimulate rural markets, benefiting traders, transporters, and agro-dealers involved in the input and output value chains (Jayne & Rashid, 2013). Additionally, by lowering maize prices nationally, the programs benefit non-beneficiary households who gain access to affordable food (Mvula & Chiweza, 2013). Thus, even those excluded from direct participation may indirectly benefit through improved market conditions

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of Malawi's Affordable Inputs Program (AIP), several critical recommendations must be implemented to address its long-standing challenges and ensure it truly serves the nation's poor and vulnerable. A foundational step is to significantly improve the beneficiary identification process, which has often been a source of inefficiency and inequity. The government must define and standardize clear, objective criteria for identifying eligible farmers, moving beyond a broad, universal approach. For instance, a "productive farmer" model could utilize objective data such as geo-referenced landholding sizes or demonstrated yields to guide selection, ensuring the subsidy supports those who can make the most productive use of the inputs (ASFAW, 2017). Such a system would help the program become more targeted and impactful, directing resources to those who can genuinely leverage the subsidy to increase production and improve their livelihoods.

Beyond simply providing inputs, a crucial recommendation is to increase investment in agricultural extension services. While the subsidy provides the necessary tools for farming, many smallholder farmers lack the knowledge to use them efficiently. Therefore, increased funding and capacity for agricultural extension programs are vital to educate farmers on proper agronomic practices, such as integrated soil fertility management and the efficient use of inputs (WALLS, 2023). This education would not only raise productivity and increase the return on the government's investment but also equip farmers with the skills needed for long-term sustainable farming, reducing their dependency on the subsidy over time.

For the AIP to be truly sustainable and resilient in the face of climate change, it must incorporate climate-smart practices. This means reducing the program's heavy dependence on inorganic

fertilizer, which is both costly and can degrade soil health over time. A more sustainable approach would be to promote a combination of inorganic and organic inputs, encouraging the use of manure, compost, and other soil-enriching practices (ROBERT, 2017). The program could also incentivize the adoption of conservation agriculture techniques, such as minimum tillage and crop rotation, which improve soil health, conserve water, and make farms more resilient to the increasingly frequent droughts and floods that plague the region.

Addressing the persistent logistical challenges of the program is another key recommendation. One of the most common complaints from farmers is the late arrival of inputs, which often reduces their effectiveness and can lead to crop failure. To combat this, the government must enforce stronger contracts with reputable agro-dealers to ensure the timely and reliable delivery of inputs to selling points across the country. Furthermore, to reduce the time and transportation costs for farmers, the number of agro-dealer outlets where inputs can be redeemed should be significantly increased, particularly in remote, rural areas (WALLS, 2023). This can be achieved by providing incentives for agro-dealers to set up satellite outlets and by strengthening public-private partnerships to improve the overall efficiency and reliability of the supply chain.

Finally, ensuring the program's integrity and effectiveness requires a strong focus on public awareness and accountability. The government should conduct widespread public awareness campaigns, utilizing local radio and community meetings, to help farmers understand their rights and responsibilities under the program (CHIRWA, 2013). By clearly communicating the official prices of inputs and the proper redemption process, these campaigns can make it harder for malpractices to occur and empower communities to hold officials and agro-dealers accountable. Creating a transparent and accessible feedback mechanism would further strengthen this system, allowing farmers to report issues and ensuring that the program operates with the highest level of integrity.

CONCLUSION

The Farm Input Subsidy Program and the Affordable Inputs Program represent Malawi's bold efforts to confront persistent poverty and food insecurity. By enhancing access to fertilizers and improved seed, these initiatives have strengthened food security, raised incomes, and provided a

form of social protection for millions of smallholder households. However, challenges of targeting, sustainability, and vulnerability to climate shocks limit their overall impact. For these program to continue addressing poverty and livelihood issues effectively, reforms must focus on improved targeting, complementary investments in rural infrastructure and extension, and strategies for climate resilience. While not a solution, FISP and AIP remain central pillars in Malawi's fight against rural poverty

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